

Mechanical and Shearographic Inspections of Stacking Sequences in Ply-Drop Composite Lay-ups

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Same prepreg material, different process parameters

- Thermoset prepreg supplied from Kordsa, AX201 XL
- Both samples are manufactured with vacuum bag only (VBO) process

Ply-drop in Composites

CFRP wing structure of Boeing's Dreamliner production line scale*

* Ullmann, Thomas, et al., DGZfP-Proceedings BB 124-CD 124 (2010).

- A design feature where plies are terminated to reduce thickness.
- Enables weight optimization and structural tailoring.

Ply-drop in Composites

- A design feature where plies are terminated to reduce thickness.
- Enables weight optimization and structural tailoring.

However,

- Resin-rich pockets
- Interlaminar stress concentrations
- Delamination and stiffness mismatches
- Manufacturing complexity

Ply-drop in Composites - Manufacturing

- Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) Process

Advantages

- Automation
- Repeatable production
- Thickness variation
- Ply orientation variation
- Low material waste

Disadvantages

- Cost of processing equipment
- Defect formation
- Restrictions of part size and shape
- Relatively slow

→ Can we have improved ply drop laminates with AFP?

Motivation

Placement of
stopper tapes

UD vs. CP

This study aims to evaluate how different stacking sequences and different AFP lay-up strategies influence the mechanical performance and damage evolution in ply-drop regions.

- Tensile test
- Acoustic emission inspection
- Shearography
- C-Scan

Sample Manufacturing

Prepreg
manufacturing

Tape slitting of
AX201-XL

AFP Lay-up: F 300N,
speed 0.1 m/s

Preform

Oven curing

Water jet
cutting

Lay-up Configurations

- Reference (REF) laminates: 8 layers → UD_REF and CP_REF

Lay-up Configurations

- Reference (REF) laminates: 8 layers \rightarrow UD_REF and CP_REF
- Ply drop (PD) laminates: 16 layers \rightarrow UD_PD and CP_PD

UD_PD

CP_PD

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Lay-up Configurations

- Reference (REF) laminates: 8 layers \rightarrow UD_REF and CP_REF
- Ply drop (PD) laminates: 16 layers \rightarrow UD_PD and CP_PD
- Ply drop with stopper (PD_ST) laminates: 16 layers \rightarrow UD_PD_ST and CP_PD_ST

UD_PD

UD_PD_ST

CP_PD

UD_PD_ST

Tensile Test

Tensile Test Results

- Elastic modulus unchanged across all UD and CP samples.
- For UD laminates:
 - Ply drop had minimal effect.
 - Stopper reduced tensile strength (~17% drop).
- For CP laminates:
 - Ply drop caused slight strength loss (~4% drop).
 - Stopper recovered strength to reference level.

→ Stopper benefits CP but weakens UD.

Tensile Test Results – UD Laminate

- Acoustic emission inspection results and sample images after test

- UD_REF:** High AE event and energy → sudden, fiber-dominated failure.
- UD_PD:** Moderate AE event and energy → localized damage near ply drop
- UD_PD_ST:** Low AE energy → stiffness mismatch → progressive, delamination-driven failure

Tensile Test Results – CP Laminate

- Acoustic emission inspection results and sample images after test

- CP_REF:** Complex damage: matrix cracking, delamination, and fiber breakage. AE profile suggests rich multi-mechanism damage evolution.
- CP_PD:** Ply drop slightly reduces AE activity; fewer damage mechanisms involved.
- CP_PD_ST:** Stopper delays crack localization, promotes more distributed energy release.

Shearography Inspection

Shearography

- A non-destructive optical technique used to detect surface and subsurface defects.
- Measures strain gradients by capturing phase-shifted speckle interferograms.

Thermal Excitation

- Halogen lamps → thermal expansion → surface deformations (real time).
- Ideal for detecting delamination, stiffness mismatches, thickness discontinuities and **resin rich-regions** in composite laminates.

Shearography Inspection

- Phase-shifted speckle interferograms are recorded and processed sequentially to compute phase differences between adjacent frames.
- Relative phase change ($\Delta\phi$, in radians) are computed from speckle patterns before and after thermal loading

- Measured signal \rightarrow shear derivative of the out-of-plane displacement ($\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$)
- Governing equation:

$$\Delta\phi = \frac{4\pi}{\lambda} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Delta x$$

λ : Laser wavelength

Δx : shear distance

$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$: deformation gradient (local surface strain)

\rightarrow Compensated shearography phase maps

Shearography Results

- Compensated shearography phase maps of UD and CP laminates under thermal excitation with interferometric shear applied along the X-direction \rightarrow Relative phase change ($\Delta\phi$, in radians)

Shearography Results

- Compensated shearography phase maps of UD and CP laminates under thermal excitation with interferometric shear applied along the X-direction \rightarrow Relative phase change ($\Delta\phi$, in radians)

- UD_REF show greater deformation contrast due to their anisotropic lay-up

- CP_REF display more uniform strain fields, due to alternating fiber directions.

Shearography Results – UD Laminate

- UD_REF
 - Uniform fringe pattern
 - Indicates structural integrity and consistent stiffness
 - No signs of localized deformation
- UD_PD
 - Distorted fringes at ply drop region
 - Suggests local stiffness variation and deformation concentration
 - Evidence of thickness-induced discontinuity
- UD_PD_ST
 - Sharper fringe gradients near ply drop
 - Stopper introduced abrupt stiffness mismatch
 - Increased out-of-plane deformation detected

Shearography Results – CP Laminate

- **CP_REF**
 - Uniform and low-contrast fringe pattern
 - Indicates balanced load distribution due to cross-ply architecture
 - No significant deformation anomalies
- **CP_PD**
 - Slight fringe disturbance at ply drop region
 - Suggests mild local strain accumulation
 - Reflects minor stiffness change from thickness variation
- **CP_PD_ST**
 - Fringe pattern nearly restored to reference condition
 - Stopper helps redistribute strain at ply drop
 - Indicates stabilized deformation behavior and improved structural continuity

Integrated Evaluation

Sample	Tensile Strength (MPa)	AE Inspection	Shearography	C-scan
UD_REF	2109.8	Fiber-dominated failure, high energy	Uniform strain field, structurally intact	High signal uniformity, no defect
UD_PD	2071.6	Localized damage near ply drop, moderate energy	Distorted fringes at ply drop, stiffness variation	Minor attenuation at drop region
UD_PD_S	1754.0	Delamination-driven failure, low energy	Abrupt gradient at stopper, increased deformation	Pronounced attenuation, localized disruption
CP_REF	1065.2	Matrix cracking + delamination + fiber breakage	Uniform low-contrast field, no anomaly	Clean signal, no defect
CP_PD	1027.4	Fewer damage mechanisms, reduced AE	Mild fringe disturbance at ply drop	Edge attenuation, stable core
CP_PD_S	1064.6	Distributed energy release, stable AE	Fringe pattern restored, strain redistribution	Bright central zone, no signal loss

Conclusion

- AFP enables more controlled and defect-minimized ply-drop transitions.
 - Ply drops reduce strength, more significantly in UD laminates.
 - Stopper application recovers performance in CP but reduces it in UD.
 - AE data captured differences in failure modes between configurations.
 - Shearography and C-scan effectively identified resin-rich and stiffness-mismatch zones.
 - All findings complement each other, providing a sophisticated understanding of failure mechanisms in ply-drop laminates.
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- Future work will investigate fatigue behavior, thermal cycling, and optimized ply drop geometries using AI-driven AFP strategies.

Thank you!

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Ultrasonic C-scan Inspection

- C-scan is a non-destructive ultrasonic inspection technique used to create a planar (2D) image of the internal condition of composite materials.
- Outputs an amplitude image of internal laminate integrity

Test Set-up:

- Immersion –tested composite panel,
- Two probes (transmitter-receiver) ,
- Frequency 1-5 MHz

Calibration:

- Sound area reference amplitude A_{ref}
- Time- correction gain or Distance Amplitude Correction (DAC)

dB Mapping:

- $A_{db} = 20\log_{10}(A_i)$
- Normalized

C-Scan Defect Map

C-scan Results

UD_REF

UD_PD

UD_PD_ST

CP_REF

CP_PD

CP_PD_ST

Microscopic Inspections

UD_PD

UD_PD_ST

Microscopic Inspections

CP_PD

CP_PD_ST

